

**Factors influencing students in choosing
media studies as a major in higher education:
A study examining ways to promote media
studies.**

by

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Declaration

The work I have submitted is my own effort. I certify that any and all the material in this Dissertation, that is not my own work, has been identified and acknowledged.

No materials are included for which a degree has been previously conferred upon me.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be the initials 'MT' or 'M.T.' with a stylized flourish.

Signed: Muhammad Taufik

Date: 31 January 2023

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Abstract

The popularity of media studies in higher education in Singapore is declining. Potential students no longer find it attractive or do not see any prospect of a career in the media industry. Higher education institutions have the responsibility to portray the media studies major correctly. There have been many related studies done around the topic of higher education. However, no specific steps have been taken to address the decline in enrolment in media studies or to promote media studies in Singapore's higher education. Additionally, it is possible that it was simply poor marketing on the part of higher education institutions. Hence, this paper attempts to address this worrying issue in media studies faculties.

The study adopted a quantitative methodology with a survey conducted with 150 respondents. Data collected were analysed with Microsoft Excel software. Hypothesis testing using T-test analysis was used to analyse the reliability of the theories. A standard error of the mean was calculated to explore the spread of the data around the mean which indicates its reliability and statistical significance. From the results, it is evident that motivation by key personnel such as lecturers/trainers and the environment in which students grow up heavily influence their decision-making in wanting to pursue media studies as a major in higher education. Furthermore, having the right management practices such as the implementation of TQM is crucial in a higher education institution's organisation. In addition, adopting the right marketing strategies such as incorporating digital marketing by utilising various social media platforms will be vital in the higher education institution's attempt to increase its enrolment in the media studies faculty.

Keywords: media studies, higher education, students, management, marketing, Singapore

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context

Education is a vital industry in Singapore (PSD, 2015). During the post-World War II period, the Singapore government determined that education is vital for achieving economic success (Goh & Gopinathan, 2008). An average Singaporean student attends primary school for six years, secondary school for four to six years, and postsecondary for one to three years as shown in Fig.1 (NCEE, 2021). The students will then continue their education at the tertiary level at any of the available higher education institutions or colleges. These institutions are either run by the government or a private entity. At this point, every student will have to decide on a major to pursue in higher education. It is a crucial phase that can essentially shape their future career based on the interests that students intend to explore.

Other independent or semi-autonomous agencies such as private education institutions (PEI) operate within the framework set by the Ministry of Education. As a complement to the public sector of education, they provide a number of educational options for some Singaporeans as well (MTI, 2018). Each of these education provider agencies has clearly defined responsibilities, and all of them work closely with the Ministry (NCEE, 2021). There are a variety of courses that is offered by both government polytechnics and universities and private education institutions. However, this research paper will concentrate primarily on one major discipline, that is media studies.

The Singapore Education Landscape

Fig.1 (NCEE, 2021)

Media studies is a field that discusses and analyses the history, content, and impact of a variety of forms of widely spread communication (NorthCentralCollege, 2019). A number of different academic disciplines fall under the umbrella of media studies. Our world is filled with a wide variety of media, which can generally be categorized into two types namely Contemporary media and Traditional media (Apuke, 2017). Social media, digital journalism, and video games are some of the modern forms of media and visual communication employed by contemporary media (Gitner, 2015). Traditional media, on the other hand, refers to older forms of media practice such as writing, radio, and TV broadcasting. (Tolson, 2010)

A concern currently is that the faculty in media studies in Singapore have seen a decline in their enrolment at higher education institutions in recent years. The latest education statistics published by the MOE shows that the number of intake for media studies at various higher education institutions having low intakes for the last two years (MOE, 2021). The number of enrolments for government polytechnics in 2020 was only 1,729 students. This is in comparison to other popular courses such as engineering & science at 19,531 and business & administration at 13,124. Likewise, semi-autonomous institutions such as NAFA and LASALLE have also seen a decline in the enrolment of their media-related diploma courses at 275 students in comparison to the fine arts and design courses which stood at 1,034 and 2,034 respectively. It comes as no surprise that this downward trend continues to be seen at the university level as well. Media degree programs at those institutes had only 81 students enrolled. In contrast, fine & performing arts had 273 students while design & applied arts were ranked the highest with 746 students (MOE, 2021). The ministry of education of Singapore's education statistics digest is a detailed and robust compilation of data analysis on the education sector. This data analysis is collected quantitatively and published each year. (see Fig.2 – Fig.9 in Appendix B)

Furthermore, private education institutions (PEI) in Singapore also observed a drop in their enrolments for their media studies majors during the Covid-19 pandemic (Leow, 2021; PwC, 2020). This is because PEI relies on foreign students to enrol in various higher education or tertiary programs offered at their institution/college. According to BusinessTimes (Ho, 2022), it is reported that as of the end of August 2021, there were approximately 59,000 international students in the country. This is a decrease of 13.5% from 68,200 at the end of April 2020, according to figures provided by the Ministry of Education (MOE) and the Immigration and Checkpoints Authority (ICA). While the authorities did not provide BusinessTimes (Ho, 2022) with historical data to compare with pre-pandemic levels, the number of students with student passes fell from 35% to 25% in private education institutions (PEIs). It adversely affects both private schools' main source of income and Singapore's ability to maintain its regional status as a hub for education (Ng, 2020). It is possible that there is a connection between this problem and

the decline in enrolment in media studies at higher education institutions. Another possible reason is the lack of marketing efforts on the part of higher education institutions.

1.2 Research Objectives

There have been several related studies done on the topic of higher education (Camilleri, 2019; Hafeez & Nauman, 2020; Oh, Chan, & Kim, 2020; Sadjali, Sansawi & Matolo, 2022). However, no specific steps have been taken to address the decline in enrolment in media studies or to promote media studies in Singapore's higher education. Hence, this paper attempts to address this worrying concern in media studies faculties. This is because it will directly impact the pool of media professionals if there is no new blood joining the industry in the future. Therefore, this research paper seeks to provide insights critical for the promotion of media studies in higher education.

The objectives of this research paper are (1) to examine the motivating factors in wanting to pursue media studies, (2), to discover the influence behind the student's decision-making in choosing a major in higher education, (3), to identify ways to increase enrolment in media studies in higher education and (4) to analyse the marketing strategy for promoting media studies in higher education.

This research paper will fulfil these research objectives by answering the following research questions:

1. What motivates the students to pursue media studies?
2. What influences the students in their decision-making when choosing a major?
3. How to increase enrolment in media studies in higher education?
4. How were media studies marketed by higher education institutions?

The next chapter will present the literature review of academic literature related to media studies in Chapter 2. This will help with the analysis of this paper. In Chapter 3, the methodology for this research will be outlined. Chapter 4 will present the findings from the analysis of the data collected. Finally, the findings of this research study will be discussed which will be discussed together with recommendations in Chapter 5 of the paper. This author hopes that, if taken into consideration by higher education institutions, these suggestions may assist in resolving the issue.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This part of the research will be a discussion of relevant academic literature on studies done that revolves around the topic “Factors influencing students in choosing media studies as a major in higher education: A study examining ways to promote media studies”. Although there have been many studies done on students' influence in choosing a major, but none of them has specifically focus on media studies. The focus is on students making choices in higher education and promoting media studies so as to answer the research questions of this paper. This will enable the author to have an in-depth understanding on the chosen topic in the deductive approach research (Gill & Johnson, 2010). To focus on the relevance of the research topic, the author of this research paper will be focusing on themes such as motivation, influence, management, marketing and industry.

2.1 Motivation - Students' motivation towards media studies

Having the right motivation to pursue a goal is crucial for everyone. In Jenkins's (2001) view, motivation can be divided into four categories. Firstly, intrinsic motivation stems from a strong interest within the individual, whereas extrinsic factors such as career or awards are the main motivations that may influence success. Meeting others' needs is the main motivation for societal. Lastly, in order to achieve personal fulfilment, completing the tasks at hand is the primary goal. It is imperative for students to be motivated in order to develop positive attitudes. Motivation will lead to a positive attitude, dedication, and persistence, whereas a deficiency of motivation leads to negativity (Berg, 2005). This is more prevalent among adolescents. This is because adolescent students are usually at an age where they prefer to listen to their peers instead of their parents for advice (Eccles & Harold, 1996). It is detrimental to a student's motivation to have the right peers. Students' motivation suffers when they don't have the right peer circles (Cowie & Wallace, 2006). When it comes to the topic of choosing a major in higher education, it is obvious that this is one of the most relevant factors to consider for adolescents. This is because the education system expects student at the end of grade 12 to make a decision in choosing a specific major (Germeijs et al., 2012). Adolescents consider college decisions, which include major selection, to be significant because they can be used as a stepping stone for future career decisions. (Lent, Brown & Hackett, 1994)

Oh et al. (2018) provides an analysis of students involved in creative media are driven by a number of critical motivators and identifies that students in that major are concerned with these three aspects which are independent learning or allowing students to control their own learning process, peer relationships since they spend the majority of the school week doing creative studio production, and relationships with industry professionals because establishing relationships with

industry professionals is crucial to finding a job after graduation. Through networking, industry professionals are able to create value to students towards the media industry (Ashton, 2011). Educators are constantly challenged by the task of motivating their students, which is a crucial part of their jobs (Caprara et al., 2006). It is imperative for supervisors to understand their students' needs as well as their motivation for learning. This is in order to be able to reinforce their students' motivation to keep on learning on a daily basis during the planning and execution of any project. In this way, they are encouraged to remain creative and innovative throughout their educational journey (Oh, 2018). In creative media courses, motivating students is crucial. Oh (2018) stresses that it is the role of educators to understand students' learning needs and motivations and to reinforce the motivation of students to remain creative throughout their learning process. Students' motivation can be enhanced in a creative media classroom with the use of social media (Oh, Chan & Kim, 2020; Oh, 2018). According to Oh, Chan and Kim (2020) by using social media in this case facebook, educators and students can now better interact, bridge communication barriers to build interpersonal relationships, and increase their motivation to learn. This article makes a strong argument for the use of social media in a conditional manner with respect to project-based learning (PBL). However, the use of social media platforms has also changed since two years ago as adolescent students have moved to other platforms such as Instagram and tik-tok. Nevertheless, students are able to build experiences, constructs, and abstract concepts by observing and participating in PBL (Helle, Tynjälä & Olkinuora, 2006; Bender, 2012). As part of their experiential learning, they also take part in learning processes that help them generalise, internalise, and conceptualise their understandings as well. As a result of this progression, students will develop their knowledge and apply it, increase engagement, achieve achievements, gain confidence, and ultimately remain motivated. An imperative aspect of influencing the learner's motivation to learn a subject is motivated by their ability to understand the subject knowledge and their achievement in that subject (Covington, 2000). Motivation can be defined in various ways, but enthusiasm for a task is probably the most basic definition (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2010). This was clearly reflected in a study by Hanusch et al. 2014 investigates the motivations, prospects, and expectations of journalism students, offering much needed comparative evidence. It states that social factors, such as the historical and socio-cultural background of the country in question, in addition to the media structures with their own norms and financial variables, can have a significant influence on journalism education. However, they also contend that students could use a journalism degree solely to break into the media industry. The study was a collaborative effort consisting of researchers from 9 different countries. This resulted in extensive surveys and tests.

In addition, Mladenovic, Zanko and Mladenovic (2015) conducted a study as the number of people enrolled in computer science degree programs has seen a gradual decline over the last few

years in Croatia because many K 12 students consider computing to be a low-importance subject. The study found that rather than being motivated by extrinsic rewards like grades or awards, students are motivated by intrinsic rewards such as constructive criticism (Deci, Koestner & Ryan, 1999; Oh, 2018). It also notes that students who are motivated to learn are more likely to put more effort into their studies and achieve more. However, Ibrahim Sharif and Suleiman Sharif (2014) mentioned in their paper that young high school graduates' choosing of university majors is influenced by a complex combination of factors and motivations, such as their interest in chemistry, biology, and mathematics, their expectations of a well-paying career, the availability of a wide range of jobs, the reputation of Universities and Colleges and the influence of their promotional activities, and the influence of their parents, relatives, and friends (Nilson, 2016). In all these studies, peer relationships and educators are consistent factors that influence students' motivation. In addition, networking was also seen as key in the studies. As such, based on the findings of the studies presented in this section, the hypothesis generated is as follows: **H1: Students who are exposed to media studies elements are more likely to choose media studies as a major in higher education.**

2.2 Influence - Students' influence in choosing a major

Choosing a tertiary education or programme to pursue is a challenge for most high school graduates. Making an informed decision is not an easy task when there are numerous elements that influence a person's decision. Choosing is influenced by cognitive factors and social structures of a person's environment, depending on his or her cognitive abilities and social situation (Lent, Brown & Hackett, 2000). Studies have shown that university education can have an influence on students' professional values and attitudes, as well as on their future work (Tomlinson, 2007; Lee 2009). Although others have shown that this influence is minimal. According to Moogan, Baron and Harris (1999), candidates seeking admission to higher education adopt different decision-making behaviours. The study examines whether or not potential students, in the context of the British educational system, follow a systematic approach, following a logical progression. It also examines whether or not they select the options with the best ranking in each step. It has been found that students are much more likely to be influenced by their friends who attend such institutions than by the opinions of their teachers and parents (Moogan & Baron, 2003; Harris & Goodall, 2008). In contrast to that, students indicate that their parents have the most significant impact on the decisions they make in their lives (Harris & Goodall, 2008). Influences from family and peers also play a significant role in choosing a course. The most likely outcome is that a student will take a degree that a friend or peer wants if he/she bases all his/her decisions on peers or friends.

Choosing a college course can be challenging for many students because they must consider many factors. While some students choose a course based on skills, interests, or expertise, others are hampered by socio-economic disadvantages. Sadjail, Sansawi, and Matolo's (2022) study in the College of Education at MSU-TCTO examined the factors that influence students when choosing a course or major. Based on the findings of this study, they found that there is a clear consensus among students. This is because parents' discretion, external influences, affordability, practicality, personal preference and interest, and socio-economic factors are the main factors that affect students' choice of courses. The same expectation was also echoed in a study by Sarkodie, Asare and Asare (2020), in which it was discovered that students' choice of tertiary education was influenced by the reputation of the institution, followed by parental influences, peer and media influences, and cost considerations. The distance between the location of campus and home was also an instrumental factor in students' decision to further their education according to Simões and Soares (2010). But that does not really apply to the Singapore context as the country has a well-developed public transport system that links almost every corner of the island.

Another influencing factor that plays a huge significant role towards adolescent students is social media. As a means of communicating information about their programs to prospective students, higher education institutions are increasingly relying on social media as an effective tool. This is because they can make their programmes known to prospective students through social media platforms (Constantinides & Zinck Stagno, 2011). According to Sola and Zia (2021), social media, especially Facebook, plays a significant role in influencing students' decision to choose a study program and higher education institution (HEI). The study indicates that each and every student uses a mobile device in order to access information. According to the researchers, social media use has become a high-level part of society due to the fact that people continually interact with each other via the Internet on various types of platforms, explaining why social media use has become universal. Through the use of a variety of modes such as online applications, messaging services, and social media, people are able to stay connected whenever they wish (Chambers, 2014). This includes absorbing news, talking with each other, making decisions, etc., without having to be physically around each other (Srivastava, 2005). This is regardless of the source of the information, and that this trend has significant implications for institutions' strategies for engaging potential students in the recruitment procedure (Rowan-Kenyon & Martinez, 2016).

According to Lee (2009), people are more likely to decide on their career at a particular time in their life than at other points in their lives. It is common for students to make decisions about their majors while seeking advice from college counselling centres. A significant number of these students seek counselling because they are unsure of what profession they would like to

choose. Furthermore, students often mention lack of motivation as hindering their decision to major in college. Grannitz, Chen, and Kohli (2014), highlighted that high school students' decision-making process is primarily driven by their own choices, but parents and family play a very crucial role in influencing those choices. There is a growing trend among students to pursue majors that offer satisfying careers and require skills they are proficient at.

There have been a number of perspectives adopted by the research community in order to provide a deeper understanding of college student's choice of major. Among these perspectives are general models based on factors such as personality, gender, income, academic ability, characteristics of the parents, factors that influence the parent-child relationship, and the impact of significant others on the outcome (Nyhus & Pons, 2005). In the process of choosing their major, students take into consideration their expected earnings and their perceived abilities, with aptitudes being more relevant than expected income streams (Zafar, 2013). Non-financial factors that can be influenced by an individual's preferences and abilities are more influential than monetary factors, with financial factors being the most significant (Grannitz, Chen, & Kohli, 2014; Ward & Sloane, 2000). Downey, McGaughey and Roach (2011) also mentioned that students are influenced in choosing a major in college by these two variables, attitude towards choice and intention to work. According to the study, students prefer majors and careers that have a high social image to those that have a lower social image. In general, men are likely to select majors that are perceived to have a high societal standing, such as those in business. Students may choose majors that seem to be easier than alternative choices because they perceive them to be easier. However, it must be said that some people make major choices based partly on how difficult or simple they think a particular major will be. In all the research studies gathered, the common factors influencing students to choose a major are parents, friends from the institute/college, career prospects, social media influences, and financial considerations.

H2: The environment that students grow up in is influential on their decision to choose a major in higher education.

2.3 Management - Management practice at higher education

The higher education industry is a competitive and ever-changing business. There are many forces that affect the higher education business, one of which is environmental. As a result of these changes, many higher education institutions have been making quality management a top priority on their agendas in order to maintain a competitive edge. A study by Becket and Brookes (2008) reveals that quality management approaches designed for industry have been adopted most often in higher education in response to external forces. The most effective approach to

managing quality in higher education remains elusive despite progress made through research and debate (Kearney, 2009). The reason for this is that quality is a complex and multifaceted concept. Many studies regarding quality management in higher education have been conducted from a single-country perspective, which explains the majority of the research (Lagrosen, Seyyed-Hashemi & Leitner, 2004). There are a number of environmental forces that are common across the Asia Pacific region such as political forces, economic forces, and socio-cultural forces (Becket & Brookes, 2008). The cultural, political, and economic forces leading to the current paradigm shift in higher education have, however, led to a culture of managerialism as a result of these forces (Levin, 2003). Additionally, there is an increasing competitive environment in higher education. This is because new higher education institutions are being built in countries such as India and Malaysia in an attempt to compete in the field (Becket & Brookes, 2008; Mohrman, Ma & Baker, 2008). Widrick, Mergen and Grant (2002) found that it has become institutionalised in many firms to apply quality management principles to industry-specific problems. Throughout the daily life of workers and management, it is an integral part of the organisation's culture.

Kemal, Suryadi and Rosyidi (2019), found that learning, teaching, and research are the three vital cornerstones of higher education management. Additionally, fostering exceptional performance among staff members, it strives to continuously improve institutional processes through responsible leadership. The key to correcting mistakes made by universities is to ensure that effective management is implemented so as to improve the quality of a college (Mohammed, Ali & Abdulaziz, 2016). This is one of the most efficient ways to make sure that the success of sustainable higher education institutions is sustained and that resource development is taken care of. This can either be done as a business or in a systematic manner. A total quality management model can take many forms. A few of the models include the Malcolm Baldrige Criteria for Performance Excellence, the European Foundation for Quality Management, the Deming Application Prize, and the ISO quality management standard (Rao Tummala & Tang, 1996). TQM is defined by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) as an approach to management focused on quality, aiming for long-term success through customer satisfaction as well as social benefits for all stakeholders (Ogbari, & Borishade, 2015). Mohammed, Ali and Abdulaziz (2016) asserted that an improved level of performance is possible by integrating administrative means, innovative effort, and specialized technical skills in the broader framework of total quality management (TQM). This way of thinking promotes continuous improvement through the integration of administrative tools, innovative work, and specialized technical skills. An academic institution's quality can be improved using the principles of TQM as demonstrated by Najafabadi, Sadeghi, and Habibzadeh (2008) in their assessment of the quality of the work that is currently completed at the University College of Boras. The public sector of a community's

economy is most dependent on education. Neither societies nor their people can survive and prosper without high-quality education. As the need for efficient, effective, and high-quality education has increased rapidly, so has the demand for explicit quality evaluation and assurance processes (Hénard, & Roseveare, 2012). Various attributes have been used by a variety of authors to measure service quality dimensions, though it remains unclear which attributes are more likely to be more effective in measuring the quality of service. The key factors that contribute to determining a good's perceived quality are performance, number of attributes, courtesy, reliability, durability, speed, aesthetics, and brand equity. These elements make up a product's or service's perception (Adam, 2015). Adam (2015) however proposed the SERVQUAL framework to examine the service quality dimensions of higher education. The framework was adapted from Garvin's 8 quality dimensions that define the quality of a product which are features, reliability, durability, performance, serviceability, conformance, perceived quality and aesthetics (Garvin, 1984). As an alternative to the more commonly used TQM model, which has gained popularity in the higher education industry, this is also an alternative.

A study by Brah, Li Wong, and Madhu Rao (2000) examines the connection between Total Quality Management and business effectiveness in Singapore's service sector. It identified a number of crucial factors for the effective application of TQM in the same sector. There is evidence in the study that TQM firms with experience perform better from the standpoint of both operating performance and financial performance compared to TQM firms without experience. Additionally, private schools in Singapore must consistently maintain a high level of quality in their education services. As well as making continual improvements, they must ensure that positive outcomes are achieved for students. Private education institutions will thus be awarded the Edutrust certificate, a quality assurance scheme administered by the CPE for Private Education Institutions (PEIs). (SSG, 2020)

However, some studies have shown that after TQM was implemented in several organizations, the performance of some of them actually worsened (Huq, 2005). Those who oppose TQM claim it is either too complicated, too costly, or too bureaucratic. Furthermore, it also claims that it stresses process over results, as well as demanding unrealistic commitment levels and formalities. (Psychogios & Priporas, 2015). It is evident from all the previous studies here that total quality management is a critical component of managing. This is made even more relevant to higher education institutes that have been struggling with getting enrolments in their media studies faculty. This can contribute to the improvement of both the operating efficiency and financial viability of higher education institutions.

H3: Higher education institutions that practice total quality management (TQM) are more likely to provide quality tertiary education.

H4: Higher education institutions that practice total quality management (TQM) are more likely to increase enrolment.

2.4 Social and economy - Media studies contribution to social and economy

The role media studies play in society and the economy has always been a question that many people, especially parents, potential students, and even government officials, have asked. To answer this question, this paper will look at the contribution and role of media to the society and economy in this theme.

At the end of the twentieth century and the beginning of the twenty-first century, media industry studies emerged as one of the subfields of media studies (Macnamara, 2010; Herbert, Lotz & Punathambekar, 2020). There is no doubt that the acquisition of relevant media studies serves as the foundation for a person wanting to work in the media industry. Hence, these workers are referred to as media professionals. Media consumption is intensive and varied among Singaporeans (Lim & Nekmat, 2009). While accessing a variety of media platforms and evaluating media content of diverse and different quality levels is increasingly challenging for them, their media literacy is being tested. According to Lim and Nekmat (2009), various media content and platforms are used in the classroom as an aid to teaching. Despite this, media education is not included in the curriculum for primary, secondary and junior colleges. Nevertheless, formal media education is more in-depth and diverse at the tertiary level than at the secondary level.

The gap in formal education for media professionals is often cited as a cause for questioning the educational credentials of media professionals. As the media industry continues to undergo rapid changes, with cutting-edge technologies emerging every day, curricula need to be updated accordingly (Kawamoto, 2003). As evidenced by Hafeez and Nauman's (2020) study, it has been discovered that media programs are very popular among young people who wish to pursue careers in the media industry, despite their neglect as an academic discipline. In addition, the author emphasised that many students are more interested in the media because it's a trend or fashion. Rather than because they want to dedicate their lives to it. As Hesmondhalgh (2010) mentions, media production studies are on the rise. Media industries themselves have grown substantially throughout the past few years due to their own rapid growth, it seems. In addition, there is an enormous amount of research and interest in the media industry in both academic circles, as well as in the media industry itself. This is because hundreds of books, seminars, and conferences, as well as countless articles and theses are devoted to it. Pumptow and Brahm (2020) for example discuss the importance of digital media usage in higher education institutions and how it benefits students in their studies. The study discovered that self-efficacy expectations affect students' media behaviour. Although in academic contexts, there is scant empirical evidence

of a link between self-efficacy in digital media and media consumption and how that relates to academic performance and socioeconomic status. In addition, the contribution of media studies to civic engagement is undoubtedly critical to society at large. Involvement in the community and civic engagement is the result of social affiliations and experiences intersecting. The concept of civic engagement can be described as the identification of public concerns, the discussion of ideas and the taking of action to address them. An individual can engage in civic engagement in many different ways. For example, it may entail direct action on a certain issue, or it may consist of working with others in the community to resolve a problem. In addition, it may involve engaging with the institutions of representative democracy. (APA, 2021)

There is almost always a perception that media use is an impediment to civic engagement, but this is not necessarily true (Shah, McLeod & Yoon, 2001). Having a sense of connectedness can enhance awareness of engaging content, such as local news. This can provide more dialogue opportunities and debate about the subtopics covered in the news, as well as make the news more accessible to the public. Research by Shah, McLeod and Yoon (2001) has shown that the combination of these two factors can significantly improve civic participation. The aim of the study is to investigate the effects of the use of media and the social context on self-reported participation in civic life and interpersonal trust in the community. It was mentioned in the study that content that mobilises the local community is more likely to make an impact in connected communities. Discussions and deliberations about topics encountered in the media have a greater chance of being engaging. Civic participation can be fostered by combining these factors. According to Livingstone and Markham (2008), the media and communication environment have also undergone transformations concurrent with these trends in civic participation. It is becoming increasingly imperative for the media to represent the government and political parties in front of the public. The cognitive engagement and social capital models of citizen participation do not take into account media consumption as a significant consequence of civic participation. These models are the only ones that include media-related variables. There is a lot of potential for emancipation and transformation in alternative media. Although these organizations are successful, they are often hindered by issues such as a limited amount of financial resources, inadequate public awareness, and as a consequence, a limited potential for societal impact due to this lack of visibility. (Sandoval, 2009).

Zhang and B. Albarran (2018) mentioned that a major driving force behind society's progress in the 21st century is globalization. Consequently, it determines how the media economy develops, in turn influencing the contribution that the media economy makes to the national economy and, therefore, its development. According to this study, the KOF Index of Globalization is used to examine whether media expenditures and globalisation are associated. Used in order to

observe changes in the level of globalisation of different countries over a period of time, the index measures the economic, social and political dimensions of globalisation. Although the topic lacks definition, it is definitely something that needs serious consideration as this has a significant affect on the future of media studies in higher education.

H5: Exposing the mass media contributes to civic engagement within society.

H6: Media studies contribute to economic growth by adding value.

2.5 Marketing - Strategic marketing in promoting media studies in higher education

In order to be able to sell effectively to their consumers, higher education institutions need to understand their needs. As of right now, there is still a great deal of confusion among higher education marketing specialists about what precisely is the impact of social media marketing on college selection decisions made by 18-year-old high school students (Sola & Zia, 2021). A study by Huang, Binney and Hede (2010) examines the first stage of a larger investigation into strategy development within higher education institutions by using two theories of competitive advantage and strategy, namely industrial organisation and a resource-based view of competitive advantage, to provide a framework for their investigation. A significant influence of sector structure on the performance of a firm can be seen in this research. The researcher adopts Porter's five-force model for the purpose of analysing the competitive environment and profitability of an industry. An approach that relies on resource-based thinking, in which the most valuable parts of a firm's resources are identified and combined with its strengths and capabilities in order to produce an approach to developing a strategy that is complementary to its strengths. According to Mathooko and Ogutu (2015), there are a number of external forces that affect the higher education industry today. As well as competitors from the public and private sectors, there are also international education providers that compete in this field. There are constant external pressures on the industry due to its position in the business triangle. This researcher outlines and justifies how Porter's five competitive forces framework can be applied to the higher education industry. It has also been identified that there are three key elements that provide a competitive advantage that is sustainable over the long term. Higher education has three key components: its branding and image, its physical characteristics, such as its location and facilities, and its delivery method, or how it is delivered. As with any other industry, the higher education industry is highly fragmented. In order to remain viable, it must be operated in a manner similar to an established business enterprise in order to survive (Huang, Binney & Hede, 2010). Students work as customers/buyers, while lecturers and trainers are regarded as suppliers, which helps to shape the business environment in an educational setting. Paulino and Castaño (2017) mentioned that marketing

models are considered to be a more suitable way to understand the behaviour of students. Therefore, educational institutions must implement marketing strategies throughout their business processes in order to influence students' decisions regarding their educational destination. As mentioned in the article, the author further elaborates on the idea that a business model is a formula that explains how a firm generates revenue and profits. In addition to this, it can also help create value for your customers as a way to create valuable relationships. Consequently, the percentage of higher education institutions implementing business strategies and acting like businesses is on the rise. This is in their pursuit of attracting lucrative international students who are willing to pay full tuition fees (Healey, 2007). Higher education marketing is inextricably linked to the forces and elements that affect businesses globally. In order to target segments effectively and understand the motivations behind these behaviours, HEIs need to better understand their markets' needs and wants (Vrontis, Thrassou & Melanithiou, 2007). As mentioned by Vrontis, Thrassou and Melanithiou (2007), identification of students' needs and wants is key to understanding the various reasons why they want to attend higher education. And it is marketers who have taken one step further to explain why this need is satisfied in order to move things forward in the marketing world. The student should determine which higher education he or she intends to pursue and gather information about the aspects that are relevant to their decision. By making the final choice, the individual is able to take into consideration everything that is offered by these various options and implement the decision by applying to the university of choice (van Deuren & Santema, (2012).

Higher education is increasingly being characterised by the application of economic theories, and it is expected that this will enhance the performance of institutions, contributing to public welfare. According to Starck and Zadeh (2013), adapting to a world where communication via the internet and various forms of technology change the way communication takes place requires universities to focus on creating value for students. Additionally, universities can attract foreign students by cooperating with other universities worldwide (Camilleri, 2019). In addition to product placement, pricing strategies, and promotional strategies, HEIs must understand the importance of efficient marketing approaches. To facilitate effective marketing of services, the 7Ps approach was proposed by the researchers. As part of the 7Ps of educational marketing, three additional Ps have been added to the marketing mix. Compared to physical products, higher education requires a different marketing mix, so adjustments need to be made. A 7P approach to services marketing includes people, process, and physical evidence. All components have different outcomes and can alter the effect of one another (Starck & Zadeh, 2013). In another study by Nemar and Vrontis (2016), it states that understanding the decision-making process (DMP) of the intended audience is crucial for marketing higher education effectively. Additionally, the study

mentions that the five-phase model of the DMP provides institutions with an assessment tool that can be used to assess the behaviour and thinking of students during the application process. It also helps universities understand how these systems interact with each other.

Camilleri's (2019) mentions that higher education institutions have to contend with intensified competition in different markets because of the aggressive growth of international students, leading to an increase in revenue for HEIs. The study also highlight the fact that higher education institutions should improve the quality of their services while at the same time delivering excellence to their customers. This will eventually impact their profitability in the long run. It is imperative that higher education institutions engage with key stakeholders, co-create value together, and take advantage of a variety of marketing tools. In addition, educational technology can be incorporated into marketing communications to improve marketing campaigns and to gain good word-of-mouth publicity from alumni and students. According to a study by Constantinides and Zinck Stagno (2011), businesses and higher education institutions are increasingly using social media to engage and interact with future students to impact the influence of social media on the choice of higher education programs and institutions. An online interactive application based on user-generated content, social media is relatively new, but growing rapidly. As a result, push marketing and traditional forms of marketing communication have lost trust and have become key factors in influencing buying behaviour.

H7: By integrating social media into marketing communications, higher education institutions will be able to improve their marketing mix.

Fig.10 Research Hypotheses Diagram

The concept diagram in Fig.10 illustrates that there are many variables that can influence and contribute to the aim of marketing media studies in higher education. With all of the hypotheses generated in this chapter, the author will decompose the research design, approach, and methodology selected in the following chapter 3. A detailed discussion of data collection and analysis methods will also be provided. Further, the limitations, feedback from the pilot test-takers, and ethical measures will be discussed in the next chapter of this paper.

3. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the methodologies that were used by researchers in the literature reviewed. This discussion will be mainly focused on qualitative and quantitative methodologies, which will be compared and contrasted in order to gain a thorough understanding of each. This will enable a better understanding of the different attributes of the two methodologies. This paper will then present the design of the research study, the theory of the model, and the methodology that will be used to conduct the research in this paper. A detailed explanation of the research methodology for the purpose of this study will be followed by an explanation of the data collection instrument. This will be accompanied by a discussion of the results of a pilot study of the survey. Finally, this research paper will also discuss the measures taken in order to address the ethical issues raised in this experiment.

3.1 Research Design and Model Theory

Model Theory

There were several relatable studies that employed qualitative methods with different variations and approaches. For example, a study by Sadjail, Sansawi, & Matolo (2022) used a phenomenological–qualitative methodology approach. In order to gain insight into elements that influence the college choices of a selected group of students, the researchers interviewed a selected target group of students. An interview guide was verified by a panel of experts for the researchers' unbiased sampling technique. Individual interviews were conducted with students at their convenience. Data from the interviews were recorded using an audio recorder and then transcribed, analysed, and interpreted afterwards. Based on the results it was found that students from lower-class socioeconomic groups enrol in education courses due to the affordability of the course and their parents' financial capabilities. Similarly Oh, Chan & Kim (2020) conducted an action research-based qualitative method in their study about how social media can be used to increase students' motivation in project-based learning. Using a similar approach to Oh's (2018) research on educators' affinity and students' motivation to learn with social media as a support tool, two types of qualitative data were gathered through journals for self-reflection and focus group interviews of 60 students. The results of the study by Oh, Chan & Kim (2020) showed that the majority of participants use social media to complete various tasks on a daily basis. From the action research and focus interviewed by Oh (2018) found, however, that the motivation level of creative media students is already high prior to joining the program as they are aware of what they want to achieve both at school and after graduation. Despite its potential bias, researchers tend to get an explanation for why people feel the way they do. The participant's experience is different from the description of the experience.

It is not the intention of this research paper to use qualitative methodology as part of the analysis. The author of this study believes that the proposed analysis approach is laborious and time-consuming to be considered for the overall analysis of the paper, and it is not feasible for implementation in a study with a limited amount of time.

Additionally, Germeijs et al. (2012) conducted a study to investigate the decision-making profile of 12th-grade students using both theory-based assumptions and data-driven procedures. A latent class cluster analysis was conducted. Out of 665 students, 422 students took part in the study, and the attrition analysis didn't reveal any difference between those who dropped out and those who continued. A more robust study by Sola & Zia (2021) analyses social media's influence on students' preferences for higher education institutions using quantitative research methods. A linear relationship was established by Pearson's correlation between two variables based on a survey of quantified survey results. Based on the results, the researchers found that 43.12% of respondents believed it would be beneficial if colleges and universities used social media applications. This is in order to provide information about their courses and education topics to international students. In addition, 27.52 percent of respondents think video information on social media can be effective, and 7.43 percent want video lectures samples. 6.12 percent believe universities should host presentations on social media. The study by Oh et al. (2018) also adopted a quantitative questionnaire containing questions that were designed by incorporating concepts from self-determination theory (SDT). Human motivation and personality are examined under self-determination theory (SDT), which classifies motivation according to whether it is autonomous or controlled (Deci & Ryan, 2012). A survey of 115 students studying in four different degree programs in film and animation was conducted by Oh et al. (2018). These students are from two different universities in Asia. The first being Hong Kong and the second being Singapore. The researcher provided a questionnaire that consisted of a 38 questions based on the 5-point Likert scale format and open-ended questions. In the survey, respondents were asked to respond to questions about various aspects of motivation and influences on them: competence, the environment in which they learn, their perception of the quality of teaching, attitudes about group-based learning, and aspirations related to the program they attended. As the researcher's intention was to examine whether motivation played a mediating role in the subject's perception of the rest of the study, the SPSS software was also used to test mediation models.

This research paper is oriented towards quantitative research methods similar to those described above. The quantitative applied research approach offers the possibility of describing and explaining phenomena as they are reflected in numerical representations and manipulations during observation. Also, this allows the author of this paper to obtain accurate and reliable

measurements that can be analysed statistically (Queirós, Faria, & Almeida, 2017). This approach will be explained further in the research design segment below.

Research Design

The purpose of this research is to identify the factors influencing students in choosing media studies as a major in higher education. As well as examining ways to promote it in the Singapore context. This research is to be completed within a three-month time frame. Since this is both an exploratory and deductive descriptive research, the author of this paper will be using the quantitative methodology. A conceptual model such as this which is based on literature findings and the recommendations that relate to the research is a conceptual study based on literature findings (Khalid, Abdullah, & Kumar, 2012). To help the author identify mitigating factors that revolve within this study, the author developed themes based on the paper's topic. By doing so, the author of this paper will be able to generate hypotheses that will be used in the creation of a questionnaire survey.

Taking into account the previous chapter, the design of this research paper is built around studies that support the hypothesis outlined in that chapter. This was for the purpose of gaining interpretive insight and comprehension based on the themes generated. The hypotheses that were formulated from all those studies are as follows:

H1: Students who are exposed to media studies elements are more likely to choose media studies as a major in higher education.

H2: The environment that students grow up in is influential on their decision to choose a major in higher education.

H3: Higher education institutions that practice total quality management (TQM) are more likely to provide quality tertiary education.

H4: Higher education institutions that practice total quality management (TQM) are more likely to increase enrolment.

H5: Exposing the mass media contributes to civic engagement within society.

H6: Media studies contribute to economic growth by adding value.

H7: By integrating social media into marketing communications, higher education institutions will be able to improve their marketing mix.

3.2 Research Approach

An explanation and justification of the methodology and research design to be used in this research paper will then be presented in the following paragraphs.

Quantitative Applied Research.

Advantages – The advantage of using a quantitative research-based study is that quantitative measurements of variables can be obtained from samples of a population. The data collection procedure and instruments incorporated into this research methodology are structured (Queirós, Faria, & Almeida, 2017). A systematic and objective approach is taken to collecting data. The applied research methodology emphasised on practical problem solving. The application aids managers and researchers in obtaining answers and the decision-making process to practical business questions regarding performance, strategy, structure, culture, organizational policy, and so forth (Khalid, Abdullah, & Kumar, 2012). Additionally, data that consists of numerical values is analysed using statistical analysis methods, using software such as SPSS, Minitab, Stata, or Microsoft Excel to name a few.

Disadvantages – The methodology is difficult to fault, but like any other methodology there are always limitations; in this case, disadvantages when it comes to implementing the method in a study. Quantitative approach depends on data from collected samples, which are based on the subjective opinions of the sample participants. (Ramona, 2011). Test-takers' and testers' experiences are not reflected in this study, because it takes snapshots rather than looking at the phenomenon in depth (Rahman, 2016). Further testing is often needed to narrow down an explanation which requires a complex process (Ramona, 2011).

3.3 Data Collection and Analysis methods

An online survey was designed using the Google Forms platform. This tool facilitates the structured data collecting process and simplifies the collection of collected data into an Excel file. There is no charge for using the platform. In an effort to reach its target faster, the link rolled around and spread according to the snowball sampling method. Participants only need to have a Google email account to participate and have their responses recorded. The research was conducted using a random sampling strategy with a group size of 150 participants. The questions are generated according to hypotheses which correspond to the variables examined. There are a total of 25 closed-ended questions in the questionnaire. Section A – Demographic uses a multiple-choice question. The Likert scale questions were used in the remaining sections which are: B – Motivation, C – Influence, D – Management, E – Social and economy, F – Marketing. This enables the participants to rate and evaluate the question of statements. The collected data were analysed using Microsoft Excel software in a statistical procedure. The data collected will be analysed to remove major errors and duplicates if any. Afterwards, Descriptive analysis whereby the mean, median, standard deviation and skewness of the sample will be analysed. This analysis method is commonly used to look for trends/patterns in the sample data collected (Mertens, Pugliese & Recker, 2016). Next, an inferential data analysis was conducted, whereby a T-test statistical analysis was adopted to test the null and alternative hypothesis with the Standard Error bar

presented together. Using this data sample, the author of this paper will be able to determine whether there are any indications of a difference or reliability between the means of the two variables' data samples. (Mertens, Pugliese & Recker, 2016)

The full survey questionnaire is attached in appendix A of this paper. Here is the breakdown of survey based on the thematic hypotheses,

(H1) Section B – This section discusses about what motivate students to study media studies. This makes up question number 7 to 10 of the questionnaire.

(H2) Section C – This section discusses the influences towards the students choosing of a major in higher education. This makes up question number 11 to 14 of the questionnaire.

(H3 & H4) Section D – This section talks about the management practise in higher education institutions. This makes up question number 15 to 18 of the questionnaire.

(H5 & H6) Section E – This section talks about media studies' contribution to social and economic development in Singapore. This makes up question number 19 to 22 of the questionnaire.

(H7) Section F - This section discusses the importance of strategic marketing to raise awareness of media studies in higher education. This makes up question number 23 to 25 of the questionnaire.

3.4 Research Limitations

Upon dissemination of the survey, the author discovered some limitations. One limitation is the fact that the survey was distributed in December, so it was difficult to get respondents to complete the survey in a timely manner. This is because most of them were probably on vacation. Furthermore, the author of this research discovered that some of the students who got the survey link were quite reluctant and unsupportive of the study. This has greatly depleted the representativeness of adolescents that the author had hoped to attract. There may be several factors behind this. One possibility could be that students are preoccupied with their assignments. Another possibility is the fact that Gen Z adolescents could view the notion of carrying out a survey as a chore and as a time waster. The author of this paper concludes, however, that perhaps young Gen Z adolescents are just being brought up differently in this digital age of social media and gaming, thus the change in behaviour. This is something worth studying in the future.

Nevertheless, a significant number of adolescents still participated in the survey. This contributed to the overall number of respondents, which was largely made up of working adults and similar. This will be presented further in the next chapter of this paper.

3.5 Pilot Testing

Pilot testing of the survey was conducted among a small group of 5 participants. The aim of this pilot test is for the author of this paper to get feedback on whether there were any difficulties the group had understanding how to answer the questions. Following the completion of the questionnaire, the common feedback that the author received was on question number 25 that stated *“For any higher education institution in Singapore, adopting the 7Ps of marketing will be essential and strategic”*. There is consensus among the participants in this study that this question can only be answered by someone who has marketing knowledge. This is in contrast to a general layperson who does not know anything about marketing. As a result, the author of this paper changed the question to *“For any higher education institution in Singapore, adopting an appropriate marketing concept will be essential and strategic”*. Changes were made immediately before the questionnaire was disseminated the following day.

3.6 Ethical Issues

Anonymising data is one way to reduce the risk of data breaches associated with the increasing collection and use of personal data. The use of anonymised personal data can serve as a source of insight for researchers while protecting individuals. Researchers can ensure personal data protection by observing the 5-step process set by PDPC for basic anonymisation. They are explained as follows:

Step 1 - Know their data, Step 2 - De-identify their data, Step 3 - Apply anonymisation techniques, Step 4 – Compute the risk, Step 5 – Manage the risks. (PDPC, 2020)

This research study took appropriate measures to safeguard the privacy of research respondents. Specifically, the personal information of those participating in the survey was not included. Participants' data was collected strictly anonymously, i.e. their identities and personal information were not collected. The survey form has reduced the granularity of the data by generalising certain collected information. Any known information that can be linked to others has been hidden and anonymized. This is in line with the guideline that is set by the Personal Data Protection Commission Singapore (PDPC, 2020).

3.7 Summary

To summarize, this study adopted a quantitative applied research approach. This is in line with the objective of collecting samples through a survey as part of the deductive study. This methodology also allows the author of this paper to collect accurate and reliable measurements that can be analysed statistically and presented in the results and evaluation of the finding chapter. The survey was designed and disseminated using the Google forms platform for the convenience of participants. This is done to accommodate the generally busy lifestyle of

participants. While Microsoft Excel software was employed for statistical analysis of the collected data whereby a two-tailed t-statistic test was conducted. One of the main reasons for choosing this software instead of other statistical software is because of its friendly approach and easy-to-learn platform, which makes it the most suitable choice for those without any fundamental training in statistics. A total of 150 respondents were required to respond to the survey, which was a requirement sample size established by the author's supervisor. Throughout the process, participants' anonymity was strictly maintained. All the results, analysis and the evaluation of findings will be examined further in the next chapter.

4. RESULTS, ANALYSIS AND EVALUATION OF FINDINGS

The previous chapter discussed how the survey was designed and how it was collected. In this chapter, results of the samples collected from the survey that was conducted will be presented. The findings emerging from the data analysis process and testing mentioned in Section 3.3, will be presented thematically in the following section. The collected data covers a diverse spectrum of participants in Singapore. The results also show the relevance of each hypothesis that is tested. This chapter begins with a look at the nominal data whereby the demographics of survey participants will be analysed.

4.1 Descriptive Data Analysis

Demographics

A total of 150 people participated in the questionnaire survey that was conducted. The categorical data is presented in its nominal representation as follows:

Fig.11

According to the data from the survey in Figure 11, 58% of respondents are male, compared with 38% who are female. At the same time, 4% of respondents chose to remain gender neutral.

In addition, the chart on the right shows that the majority of respondents across the two age groups are aged between 18 and 29 as well as 40 and 49. Both of these age groups account for 36% respectively. Moreover, 25.3% of respondents were between the ages of 30 and 39. The rest, 2.7%, was made up of individuals aged 50 to 59 and 60 and above. Moreover, the results of the survey are in line with the results of the respondents' employment status, which can be found below.

Fig.12

In Figure12, The first chart clearly shows that 76.7% of participants are employed, while students make up 18.7% of respondents. Completing the chart above, there were 3.3% of the respondents who were not currently employed, while 1.3% of the respondents were homemakers.

The chart on the right shows that Singaporeans were the dominant respondents at 67.3%, which was unsurprising since the survey was conducted in Singapore. Singapore PR was the second-highest responder at 16.7%. At the same time, there was an equal amount of respondents with a Singapore Long-Term Pass and non-residents with 8%. These respondents are not considered outliers as they are assumed to be foreign citizens residing in Singapore who are either working or studying. The majority of these respondents 62.7% have completed either a diploma or an undergraduate degree. Likewise, the majority of these respondents come from a middle-class socioeconomic background. This is presented in Fig.13 below.

Fig.13

The chart in Figure 13, shows that 20.7% of respondents have completed either a postgraduate degree or a doctorate. The rest of the chart is made up of individuals that completed either a Nitec or Higher Nitec certificate, and an 'O' or 'N' level certificate.

The respondents' socioeconomic status is also scattered between three classifications as shown, whereby 60% are middle class, 18% are lower middle class and 15.3% are higher middle class. At the same time the rest of the respondents are made up of upper class at 4.7% and lower-class at 2%. In conclusion, this survey was able to conduct a successful survey by drawing a wide range of dynamic demographic respondents, ensuring a robust study.

This research paper will proceed to present the ordinal data that was collected from the samples in the following section. It will be based on the responses to each question in the survey form and will be based on the thematic sections of the survey form.

Section B – Motivation

7. The lecturers & trainers can inspire me to further my knowledge of media studies.

8. I am motivated to enrol in media studies after meeting the lecturers at an education expo/open house.

9. I am motivated to pursue media studies as I will be able to work with professionals in the media industry.

10. I will choose to study a media-related course if my friends are in it.

Table 1

N = 150	Mean	Median	Std dev.	Skewness	Variance	Kurtosis
Question 7	3.87	4	0.77	-1.314	0.59	3.251
Question 8	3.59	4	0.92	-0.829	0.85	0.905
Question 9	3.54	4	0.97	-0.634	0.93	0.494
Question 10	2.74	3	1.07	0.071	1.15	-0.615

The highest mean from this section as shown in Table 1 was the question on whether lecturers & trainers can inspire students to further knowledge of media studies (3.87). On the other hand, the lowest mean for the section was on the question if participants would choose a media-related course if their friends were enrolled (2.74). This shows the importance of lecturers and trainers as role models in motivating potential students to choose media studies.

Section C – Influence

11. I would not choose media studies as a major if my parents disallowed it.
12. I chose to pursue media studies based on the influences of social media.
13. Students choose a major to pursue based on its career prospects.
14. Students are more likely to choose media studies as a major to pursue in higher education based on the influence of the people around them.

Table 2

N = 150	Mean	Median	Std dev.	Skewness	Variance	Kurtosis
Question 11	2.90	3	1.17	-0.136	1.37	-0.904
Question 12	3.04	3	1.03	-0.343	1.06	-0.311
Question 13	3.86	4	0.92	-1.186	0.85	1.997
Question 14	3.57	4	0.92	1.077	0.85	0.908

The leading mean value in this section as shown in Table 2 is on the question of choosing a major to pursue based on its career prospects (3.86) that was highly agreed by the general public. In contrast, the question regarding whether participants would not choose media studies as a major if their parents disallowed it had the lowest mean (2.90) which is surprising since Asians are known for highly respecting their families. Also, this shows that participants are highly influenced by majors with positive career prospects.

Section D – Management

15. It is the HEIs responsibility to provide a quality tertiary program for students.
16. Higher education institutions will be able to attract, retain and motivate educators if total quality management (TQM) is being practiced in their organisation.
17. Adopting total quality management (TQM) practices can improve HEIs' reputation and increase their enrolment.
18. Potential students are more likely to enrol at a higher education institute based on its stellar reputation.

Table 3

N = 150	Mean	Median	Std dev.	Skewness	Variance	Kurtosis
Question 15	3.97	4	0.85	-1.309	0.73	3.019
Question 16	3.77	4	0.79	-0.877	0.62	1.878
Question 17	3.74	4	0.75	-0.762	0.57	1.544
Question 18	4.04	4	0.89	-0.892	0.79	1.096

For this section, Table 3 shows the highest mean value for potential students believing they are more likely to enrol at a higher education institute based on its reputation (4.04), which is to be expected since HEIs remain competitive. Comparatively, the lowest average was based on a question about how adopting total quality management practices can improve HEI's reputation and increase enrolment (3.74) that was disagreed with by the general public. There is some evidence that the reputation of higher education institutions affects the decision-making process of potential students.

Section E – Social and economy

19. Traditional media and new media are equally effective at influencing civic engagement within society.

20. People are more engaged and connected civically through the mass media.

21. The ability of HEIs to produce competent graduates will add value to the media industry.

22. As an individual who is interested in a career in the media industry, I would consider it if I knew that it was a stable industry that contributes to the economy.

Table 4

N = 150	Mean	Median	Std dev.	Skewness	Variance	Kurtosis
Question 19	3.70	4	0.78	-0.722	0.61	1.179
Question 20	3.95	4	0.79	-0.970	0.63	1.921
Question 21	4.13	4	0.88	-0.804	0.77	0.211
Question 22	4.01	4	0.89	-0.985	0.80	1.296

For this section, the highest mean score is on the question that states that HEIs ability to produce competent graduates will add value to the media industry (4.13) as shown in Table 4. While the

lowest mean is on the question of whether traditional media and new media are equally effective in influencing civic engagement in society (3.70). It was obvious that the general public agreed that the ability of HEIs to produce competent graduates will be crucial to the media industry.

Section F – Marketing

23. Social media is the most powerful tool in promoting a product to the young adolescents market.

24. Social media marketing is a highly effective platform for a business like higher education institutions to reach prospect students to enrol in media studies.

25. For any higher education institution in Singapore, adopting an appropriate marketing concept will be essential and strategic.

Table 5

N = 150	Mean	Median	Std dev.	Skewness	Variance	Kurtosis
Question 23	4.32	4.5	0.86	-1.628	0.74	3.331
Question 24	4.27	4	0.86	-1.399	0.74	2.307
Question 25	3.89	4	0.76	-1.022	0.58	2.810

According to this section's mean in Table 5, the general consensus is that social media is the most powerful tool for promoting young adults (4.32). There was mixed reaction towards the question that it is essential and strategic for higher education in Singapore to adopt an appropriate marketing concept, as it was the lowest mean score for the section (3.89).

The next part of this research paper will concern itself with the data samples that are collected from all of the other themes of the hypotheses. This will be presented in the next section 4.2 of Chapter 4 below.

4.2 Hypothesis Testing using T-test Analysis

As mentioned in Section 3.3 of Chapter 3, this study conducted a two-tailed T-test statistical analysis (*P*) to test the null and alternative hypothesis for each theme. The t-test statistical method is widely used by statisticians as a tool to find significant differences between two variables (Xu et al., 2017). Researchers are able to formulate predictions from the data gathered, as a result of the analysis conducted, using this methodology. An expression of statistical significance is the P-value, which represents the degree of statistical significance. In this study, a statistical test will be used to determine the probability of the outcome of a difference in mean scores (Lakens, 2013). It is based on the assumption that there is no difference between the null hypothesis and the alternative

hypothesis that this is true. As a result, inference statements will be generated for the study a result of this process. All the hypotheses in this study were supported at a confidence level of 95%. Since the author has no expectations about the direction of a difference between the two variables, a two-tailed test was used. The significance level for this study is set at $\alpha = 0.05$

4.2.1 Student and Media Studies

H1_o: Students who are exposed to media studies elements are not likely to choose media studies as a major in higher education.

H1_a: Students who are exposed to media studies elements are more likely to choose media studies as a major in higher education.

Table 6

	<i>Students</i>	<i>Media studies</i>
Mean	82.75	25
Variance	1219.583333	588.6666667
Observations	150	150
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Standard error	2.851412905	1.981021061
df	2	
t Stat	2.716143727	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.02098373	
t Critical one-tail	2.015048373	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.04196746	
t Critical two-tail	2.570581836	

Results from Microsoft Excel in Table 6 show that it is statistically significant that students exposed to media studies elements are more likely to choose media studies as their major in higher education. Due to the fact that the P value = .04 is smaller than alpha, H1_o has been rejected, while H1_a has been supported.

Fig.14

The chart in Figure14 shows the standard error based on the mean of the two variables, students

(2.85) and media studies (1.98). The error bar shows a long range of values, which indicates that they are less reliable and spread out. Standard deviation error bars indicate whether a difference is significant when plotted on a graph (Cumming, Fidler and Vaux, 2007). There is no overlap between the mean bars. A non-overlapping standard deviation error bar signals a significant difference (Krzywinski & Altman, 2013). As explained by Cumming, Fidler & Vaux (2007), researchers can use the mean of the data, along with SE or CI error bars, to determine the range in which the mean of the entire possible set of results, or the entire population, would occur.

4.2.2 Environment and Decision to Choose A Major

H2o: The environment that students grow up in does not influence their decision to choose a major in higher education.

H2a: The environment that students grow up in is influential on their decision to choose a major in higher education.

Table 7

	<i>Environment</i>	<i>Major in higher education</i>
Mean	79.25	30.75
Variance	1050.916667	372.9166667
Observations	150	150
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Standard error	2.646905951	1.576740661
df	2	
t Stat	2.570645299	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.024998075	
t Critical one-tail	2.015048373	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.049996149	
t Critical two-tail	2.570581836	

On the basis of the results of Microsoft Excel in Table 7, it is statistically significant that the environment in which students grow up influences their decision to pursue a major in media in higher education. As the P value = .049 was smaller than alpha, H2o was rejected, whereas H2a was accepted.

Fig.15

The chart in Figure 15 presents the standard error based on the mean of the two variables, environment (2.65) and major in higher education (1.58). A long range of error values is again evident in the error bar as shown in Figure 15, indicating that these values are less reliable and spread out around the mean. Additionally, there is no overlap between the mean bars.

4.2.3 Total Quality Management and Quality Tertiary Education

H3o: Higher education institutions that practice total quality management (TQM) are not likely to provide quality tertiary education.

H3a: Higher education institutions that practice total quality management (TQM) are more likely to provide quality tertiary education.

Table 8

	<i>TQM</i>	<i>Quality tertiary education</i>
Mean	112.5	6.5
Variance	112.5	0.5
Observations	150	150
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Standard error	0.866025404	0.057735027
df	2	
t Stat	14.10203023	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.022534199	
t Critical one-tail	6.313751515	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.045068397	
t Critical two-tail	12.70620474	

A summary of the Microsoft Excel analysis in Table 8 indicate it is statistically significant that higher education institutions that practice total quality management are more likely to provide quality tertiary education. In view of the fact that the *P* value = .04 is smaller than alpha, H3o has been rejected, whereas H3a has been accepted.

Fig.16

The chart in Figure 16 illustrates the standard error based on the mean of the two variables, TQM (.866) and quality tertiary education (.058). There is a short range of values within the error bar, indicating that the values are more reliable and less dispersed around the mean. The mean bars as seen here do not overlap.

4.2.4 Total Quality Management and Increase Enrolment

H4o: Higher education institutions that practice total quality management (TQM) are not likely to increase enrolment.

H4a: Higher education institutions that practice total quality management (TQM) are more likely to increase enrolment.

Table 9

	<i>TQM</i>	<i>Increase enrolment</i>
Mean	108	6
Variance	50	2
Observations	150	150
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Standard error	0.577350269	0.115470054
df	2	
t Stat	20.00384578	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.015899199	
t Critical one-tail	6.313751515	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.031798398	
t Critical two-tail	12.70620474	

According to the results of the Microsoft Excel analysis in Table 9, it is statistically significant that higher education institutions that practice total quality management are more likely to provide quality tertiary education. H4o has been rejected based on the fact that the *P* value = .03 is smaller than alpha, while H4a has been accepted.

Fig.17

The chart in Figure 17 illustrates the standard error calculated from the mean of the two variables, TQM (.577) and increase enrolment (.115). There is a short range of values within the error bar, indicating that the data are more reliable and less dispersed around the mean. There is again no overlap between the mean bars. It is an indication however that there is no statistically significant difference when the standard deviation error bars overlap substantially. The lesser the overlap between the standard deviation error bars, the less statistically significant the difference is. (Krzywinski & Altman, 2013)

4.2.5 Mass Media and Civic Engagement

H5_o: Exposing the mass media does not contribute to civic engagement within society.

H5_a: Exposing the mass media contributes to civic engagement within society.

Table 10

	<i>Mass media</i>	<i>Society</i>
Mean	110	8.5
Variance	162	4.5
Observations	150	150
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Standard error	1.039230485	0.173205081
df	2	
t Stat	11.12433147	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.028537142	
t Critical one-tail	6.313751515	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.057074284	
t Critical two-tail	12.70620474	

According to Microsoft Excel analysis in Table 10, exposing the mass media to civic engagement is not statistically significant. Due to the fact that the *P* value = .06 is larger than alpha, H5_o failed to reject, suggesting that H5_a is not supported.

Fig.18

Based on the mean of the two variables, mass media (1.04) and society (.173), the chart in Figure 18 illustrates the standard error calculated. There is a short range of values within the error bar, which indicates that the data are more reliable and less dispersed around the mean. Neither mean bar overlaps with the other.

4.2.6 Media Studies and Economic Growth

H6o: Media studies do not contribute to economic growth by adding value.

H6a: Media studies contribute to economic growth by adding value.

Table 11

	<i>Media studies</i>	<i>Economic growth</i>
Mean	130	7
Variance	392	2
Observations	150	150
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Standard error	1.616580754	0.115470054
df	2	
t Stat	8.763387149	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.036166264	
t Critical one-tail	6.313751515	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.072332528	
t Critical two-tail	12.70620474	

In the analysis carried out with Microsoft Excel in Table 11, the contribution of media studies to economic growth did not show any statistical significance. Considering that the value of $P = .07$ is larger than alpha, H6o failed to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that H6a does not support the null hypothesis.

Fig.19

On the basis of the mean of the two variables, media studies (1.62) and economic growth (.115), Figure 19 illustrates the calculated standard error. An error bar with a longer range of values as shown here indicates that the data or values are less reliable and are more dispersed around the mean. It is evident that neither average bar overlaps the other.

4.2.7 Social Media and Marketing Mix

H7o: By integrating social media into marketing communications, higher education institutions would not be able to improve their marketing mix.

H7a: By integrating social media into marketing communications, higher education institutions will be able to improve their marketing mix.

Table 12

	<i>Social media</i>	<i>Marketing mix</i>
Mean	125.7	5.7
Variance	86.3	2.3
Observations	150	150
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Standard error	0.758653778	0.124721913
df	2	
t Stat	22.07301622	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.001023086	
t Critical one-tail	2.91998558	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.002046172	
t Critical two-tail	4.30265273	

According to a Microsoft Excel analysis in Table 12, it is statistically significant. This is because higher education institutions are likely to improve their marketing mix by integrating social media into their marketing communications. As a result of the fact that the $P < .002$ is smaller than alpha, H7o has been rejected, whereas H7a has been accepted.

Fig.20

According to Figure 20, the standard error has been calculated based on the means of the two variables, social media (.759) and marketing mix (.125). As shown here, an error bar with a small range of values indicates that the data are more reliable and less dispersed around the mean. The average bars do not overlap, which suggests strong significance.

This concludes the results and analysis of the findings presented in the statistical tests done in reliance on the samples that were collected. The next chapter of the research paper will discuss the findings from the research and present a summary of the hypotheses. Research objectives and questions will be addressed based on those findings. At the same time recommendations will also be made based on those findings. The information collected throughout this research study will be synthesised to draw a conclusion.

5. CONCLUSIONS, DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The intention of this research paper is to address the decline in enrolment in media studies by analysing students' decision-making and looking at strategies to promote media studies in Singapore's higher education. In Chapter 5, the author of this paper will discuss the results of the hypothesis testing done in the previous chapter. In addition, the author will discuss all the research questions formulated at the beginning of the research and link these to the literature review in Chapter 2. They will then be aligned with the research objectives set at the beginning of this research in Section 1.2 of Chapter 1. This will enable the author to conclude if this research has managed to meet its objectives or not. Consequently, appropriate recommendations will be provided and a probability of a continuation of the investigation will be determined based on those findings. Additionally, a brief discussion of adaptable organization practice and digital marketing will be presented in Section 5.4 of this chapter.

5.1 Discussion

The following is a summary of the results based on thematic hypotheses.

Section B – **Motivation:** Student and Media Studies

H1_a: Students who are exposed to media studies elements are more likely to choose media studies as a major in higher education.

On the basis of the results of the test of this hypothesis, it appears that a majority of respondents agree with and accept the statement. According to the evidence presented, the alternative hypothesis statement is strongly supported by the data. This is clear evidence of the importance of motivation for students choosing to pursue media studies as a major in higher education.

Section C – **Influence:** Environment and Decision To Choose A Major

H2_a: The environment that students grow up in is influential on their decision to choose a major in higher education.

This theme's hypothesis test shows that the statement is supported by the majority of respondents. Based on the evidence of the test, the alternative hypothesis is strongly supported, and so the null hypothesis is rejected. This also proves that the environment in which students grow up heavily influences their decision-making.

Section D – **Management:** Total Quality Management and Quality Tertiary Education, Total Quality Management and Increase Enrolment

H3_a: Higher education institutions that practice total quality management (TQM) are more likely to provide quality tertiary education.

H4a: Higher education institutions that practice total quality management (TQM) are more likely to increase enrolment.

In this theme there were two hypotheses that were generated. Results from the hypothesis testing for both statements ironically shows the alternative hypothesis was strongly supported and reliable. The results also indicate that both sets of data are less dispersed around the mean, which suggests that the data is more reliable and significant. This indicates the importance of TQM in the management practice of higher education institutions.

Section E – **Social and economy:** Mass Media and Civic Engagement, Media Studies and Economic Growth

H5o: Exposing the mass media does not contribute to civic engagement within society.

H6o: Media studies do not contribute to economic growth by adding value.

Two other hypotheses were generated on this theme, but each one had a different interpretation. According to the statistical analysis that was conducted, both hypotheses failed to reject the null hypothesis; this also indicates the alternative does not support the null hypothesis. However, H5o has a short range of values within the standard error of the mean bar as reported. This shows that the data is more reliable as the data are more clustered around the mean. In comparison, H6o has a longer range of values within the standard error of mean bar as shown in Section 4.2.6 indicating that the data are less reliable as the data are more dispersed around the mean.

Section F – **Marketing:** Social Media and Marketing Mix

H7a: By integrating social media into marketing communications, higher education institutions will be able to improve their marketing mix.

According to the results of the statistical test on this hypothesis, the majority of respondents agree with the statement and accept it. It is strong evidence that the alternative hypothesis statement is more significant and is well supported. Suggesting that integrating social media into the marketing mix is an option for higher education institutions to improve their marketing mix.

Answering the research questions.

1. What motivates the students to pursue media studies?

From the findings above, it shows that there is clear evidence that exposing students to media studies elements will motivate them to choose media studies as a major in higher education. This study supports the relevant study conducted by Oh et al. (2018) which mentions that exposing students to media-related elements helps in motivating creative media students in studying and pursuing a career in the media industry. This is mainly because most of the potential students are

unfamiliar with media studies in general. Understanding subject knowledge and achievement in a subject is the motivation of a learner toward the subject (Covington, 2000). As most media studies focus more on project-based learning, Oh, Chan and Kim (2020) mentioned that using media elements such as social media can also increase students' motivation to learn. Therefore, it can be concluded that exposure to any type of media element can motivate students to choose media studies as a major in higher education.

2. What influences the students in their decision-making when choosing a major?

In this study, it is evident that students' environment and the society that they grow up in play a key part in influencing their choice of major when they enter higher education. This is followed by peers, parents, and teachers, which correspond to those mentioned in the Moogan and Baron (2003) study. This was further confirmed by Sarkodie, Asare and Asare (2020) as they discovered that parental influences, peer and media influences, and cost considerations influenced students' choice of tertiary education. In addition, Downey, McGaughey and Roach (2011) mention that students are more inclined to choose careers or majors that have a high social image than those that have a low social image. This all contributes to the decision-making of a student in choosing a major since all of these aspects are seen as being part of the social and environmental context, which ultimately impacts their choice.

3. How to increase enrolment in media studies in higher education?

The above analysis indicated that the ability of higher education institution in adopting total quality management (TQM) practice can contribute to the likelihood of increase enrolment at higher education in general. Mohammed, Ali, and Abdulaziz (2016) supports the theory presented by the author of this research paper. According to that study, continuous improvement can be achieved through the integration of administrative tools, innovative work, and specialized technical skills. Furthermore, Najafabadi, Sadeghi, and Habibzadeh (2008) mentioned that an academic institution's quality can be improved using the principles of TQM as neither societies nor their people can survive and prosper without high-quality education. Brah, Li Wong, and Madhu Rao (2000) echoed that sentiment as their study mentions that TQM firms with experience perform better from the standpoint of both operating performance and financial performance compared to TQM firms without experience. The study clearly shows that higher education institutions could provide quality tertiary education by changing their management practices, thus increasing enrolment rates.

4. How were media studies marketed by higher education institutions?

The analysis and findings on how media studies are marketed by higher education institutions have two different dimensions based on the analysed results above. In general, there was a consensus that shows integrating social media into marketing communications will be able to improve higher education institution's marketing mix. This study supports Starck and Zadeh (2013) study that emphasised implementation of the 7Ps approach to service marketing in higher education with the focus on the three additional Ps which are people, process, and physical evidence. Constantinides and Zinck Stagno (2011) specifically mention the increasing role that social media plays in helping higher education institutions to engage and interact with future students in an attempt to understand how they make the choice of higher education programs and institutions. However there is also a contradicting factor to in the findings whereby the role of media towards society engagement and economy growth is not supported. This is in contrast to the literature by Shah, McLeod and Yoon (2001), and Livingstone and Markham (2008) that argues how mass media can create a sense of connectedness and enhance awareness within society as it promotes participation within the community. Likewise for economic growth through media studies, as mentioned in a study by Zhang and B. Albarran (2018) that states how the media economy develops can influence the contribution to the national economy. Even though the findings are less supported, the results can still be considered less reliable as outlined in 4.2.6. It is worth mentioning that the author of this paper put forward that despite the contrary findings of the literature review, it is still believed that mass media do have some role in contributing to civic engagement in society and that media studies actually does contribute to economic growth.

5.2 Limitations of the study

The results and findings of this study confirm the hypotheses presented in the research paper, but there are several limitations that must be acknowledged. At the start of this research paper, the author of this paper intended to use mixed methodology for the study. In light of the amount of work necessary to complete the mixed methodology research, and the time factor associated with the dissertation, the author decided to just use quantitative research methodology after discussion with people in the academic field. This research paper might not be comparable to those of an experienced researcher. The biggest hurdle that the author faced as a novice researcher was learning statistical analysis. Understanding the complex methods and theories of statistical analysis can be difficult to grasp and requires a lot of practice. As a novice researcher, the author may not have had enough time to develop the necessary skills for

understanding and applying statistical analysis to the research paper. Despite this, the author mastered the basic understanding of the different types of testing and chose the most appropriate analysis test for the sample data that was collected.

5.3 Recommendations

There is definitely a need for further research in light of the outcomes and results of this study. This could be a totally reworked research study based on the fact that the latest data stats will be available after the Singapore education statistics digest has been updated. Ideally adopting a qualitative research methodology will suit future studies. This is because it allows the future researcher to tailor the focus group study towards understanding the root of the problem directly, rather than merely getting random respondents. As a result, a more comprehensive understanding and view of the marketing of media studies in higher education institutions can be gained. This will increase the enrolment in this particular major at those institutions. Lastly, to have an impactful and robust research, it is suggested to also include the enrolment data of media studies courses at private education institutions (PEIs) other than those tertiary institutions run by the government of Singapore. This will create a better overview of the whole media studies landscape in the country of focus. It is pertinent to note that the decline in enrolment in media studies may not be entirely due to poor marketing on the part of higher education institutions. There may be other factors at play, such as the changing landscape of the media industry or the increasing popularity of other courses of study. This is another area that is worth exploring for future researchers to consider.

5.4 Conclusions

The objectives of this research paper from the beginning of the study are to first determine the motivating factors in wanting to pursue media studies. This can be answered from the findings that indicate motivation from key personnel such as lecturers/trainers, friends and parents played an instrumental role in students wanting to choose media study in higher education.

Secondly, the study discovered that the environment a student grew up in is definitely influential on their decision-making in selecting a course of study in higher education. This can be translated as the society and culture that students are brought up in, and their socioeconomic status is considered an influential environment.

Thirdly, in an attempt to identify ways to increase enrolment in media studies in higher education, the study identified that adopting total quality management (TQM) practice can

contribute to the likelihood of increasing enrolment in higher education. This translates mainly to the management style and practices of higher education institutions which will be explained next.

A key part of total quality management (TQM) is taking care of the customers' needs. Most of the successful organizations have realized that customer satisfaction directly affects their bottom line. A structured and systematic process is needed in order to create an environment that supports a quality culture. Lotich (2016) mentioned extensively that implementing a total quality management can be defined as these twelve steps:

1. Clarify your vision, mission, and values to your employees.

An employee should know where the organisation in this case the higher education institutions (HEI) is heading in terms of its vision, what the organisation intends to achieve with its mission and the core values that govern its decisions and priorities.

2. Identify the critical success factors (CSF).

HEI organisations must identify the critical success factors in order to focus on the things that will help them meet their objectives. As a result, they will be able to achieve their mission more effectively.

3. Develop metrics and measures to track CSF data in a systematic manner.

It is imperative to have measurements to keep track of progress and monitor it. As an example, this could be accomplished through a reporting system that shares specific data with the leadership of HEIs.

4. Determine the key groups of customers.

This is significant, as every organisation has its own customers. Understanding the needs of the key customer groups will allow HEI organisations to provide them with tailored products and services.

5. Feedback from customers should be solicited

In order for HEI organisations to know how well they are satisfying customer needs, it is necessary to create an organized process to collect feedback from customers. It is imperative to realise that what a customer expects today is very different from what they expected five years ago.

6. A survey tool should be developed

It is imperative to create a high-quality product, in this case, a tertiary programme. In addition, developing a tool for measuring customer satisfaction is essential. This is in line with what customers expect.

7. Every customer group should be surveyed

HEI organisations can establish baseline data on customers' perceptions of current practice by creating a customised survey for each customer group.

8. A plan for improvement should be developed

It is recommended that HEIs have an improvement plan for each department based on customer feedback. This plan should be written in a specific, measurable, attainable, realistic and timely format once the baseline has been established.

9. A re-survey is needed to determine whether it is working

To ensure long-term success, it is necessary for HEIs to remain in tune with changing customer needs and expectations. After implementation of the improvement strategy, observe whether customers notice a difference.

10. The CSF should be monitored

Ensure consistent progress is being made toward goals by monitoring CSF on a monthly basis. In addition, this procedure enables HEIs to make course corrections in the event that priorities or objectives change during the evaluation period.

11. Ensure that marketing plans are based on satisfaction data

In order to provide exceptional products and services, customers are interested in how the HEI organisation's internal processes work.

12. Keep up with modern technology

The use of technology facilitates the completion of work. HEIs should take advantage of technology and ensure that it is user-friendly and supports targeted improvements by ensuring that it is kept up with the changes.

These steps represent a detailed summary of how any organisation, especially a higher education institution, can adopt the Total Quality Management model. This is if it wishes to enhance its education business.

The last aim of the study was to analyse the promotion of media studies in higher education through marketing strategies. For this, the study identified that integrating social media into marketing communications will potentially be able to improve higher education institution's marketing mix. It might seem common sense to tap into digitalisation for marketing especially in the era of technology. However, there are still organizations that are still running with an old school marketing approach and failing to adapt to digital marketing. Organisation such as higher education institutions needs to know that through their ability to market media studies will not

only improve enrolments, but also add value to the industry and economy simultaneously. A good example of this is the National Technological University in Singapore's aim to develop various student engagement programmes and activities such as internships and co-creation of content with industry practitioners (CNA, 2022). As a result, the university will be able to nurture future media professionals and prepare students for entry into the industry after graduation. These future professionals will be the ones producing content for both television and cinema. Their valuable contributions to the media industry can be viewed as contributing to economic growth. The reason for this is because content that is produced locally is sold globally to providers such as Netflix (Brennan, 2018). These providers use it to localise their platforms in different parts of the world.

Higher education institutions have to take advantage of the ever-rising digital marketing platforms such as social media since this is the most impactful way of reaching out to potential students. According to a study by the nonprofit Common Sense Media published in *The New York Times* (Moyer, 2022), screen time among teens and adolescents increased by 17 per cent from 2019 to 2021 - a larger increase than four years earlier. Teens (ages 8 to 12) spend on average five hours and 33 minutes watching screen time daily, an increase of four hours and 44 minutes, and teenagers (ages 13 to 18) spend eight hours and 39 minutes watching screen time daily. *The Straits Times* (2022) reported in June 2022 that on average, Singaporeans aged 16 and older spend two hours and 30 minutes a day on social media. This is according to a survey conducted by Milieu Insight between May and June that is published in the paper.

Both organizations and individuals have equal access to online marketing due to its global nature. Reinartz & Kumar (2003) indicates that 34% of the planet's population has Internet access, providing a way to disseminate information in a way never seen before. This can be translated into a higher education institution, for instance, this clearly shows how powerful the use of digital marketing can be in terms of increasing enrolment and student retention. *The Straits Times* (2022) recently published an article that stated that universities have to prepare for a world in which their location and reputation will become less significant. This is because the world is moving toward globalisation. There is no doubt that learners will be motivated to enrol in programs that will support their ability to go to the jobs they aspire to. Thus, it is imperative and beneficial for higher education institutions to utilise the various digital marketing platforms to market the programs they offer including media studies.

The author of this paper intends to draw attention to a few of the issues that it intends to raise during the research process. Furthermore, the author of this paper hopes to make potential college students and university management aware of the importance of media studies in colleges and universities.

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7. Appendices

Appendix A

Survey Questionnaire

Dear Sir/Ma'am,

Good day! My name is Muhammad Taufik and I am completing my MBA program at Roehampton University. Hence, I would be pleased to invite you to participate in a survey on promoting media studies at higher education institutions in Singapore. It will take approximately 5-10 minutes to complete the survey. Respondents will be kept anonymous. All collected data will be strictly used for research purposes and disposed of at the end of February. This form mainly uses Likert scales and multiple-choice questions. Feel free to email me at binshaim@roehampton.ac.uk if you have any questions.

I would like to thank you in advance for your participation.

Section A – Demographic

1. What is your gender?

Male Female Others Prefer not to say

2. What age group do you belong to?

18 – 29 30 – 39 40 – 49 50 – 59 60 and above

3. What is your residency status?

Singapore Citizen Singapore PR Singapore Long Term Pass holder Non-resident

4. What is your highest level of education attained?

'O'/'N' Levels Nitec/Higher Nitec Diploma/Undergraduate Postgraduate/Doctorate

5. What is your socioeconomic status?

Lower class Lower middle class Middle class Upper middle class Upper class

6. Which of these most closely describes you?

Employed Homemaker Student Not currently employed Retired

Section B – **Motivation** (Indicate 1 – Strongly disagree, 2 – Disagree, 3 – Neither agree nor disagree, 4 – Agree, 5 – Strongly agree)

This section discusses what motivates students to study media studies.

7. The lecturers & trainers can inspire me to further my knowledge of media studies:

8. I am motivated to enrol in media studies after meeting the lecturers at an education expo/open house:

9. I am motivated to pursue media studies as I will be able to work with professionals in the media industry:

10. I will choose to study a media-related course if my friends are in it:

Section C – **Influence** (Indicate 1 – Strongly disagree, 2 – Disagree, 3 – Neither agree nor disagree, 4 – Agree, 5 – Strongly agree)

This section talks about students' influence on choosing a major.

11. I would not choose media studies as a major if my parents disallowed it:

12. I chose to pursue media studies based on the influences of social media:

13. Students choose a major to pursue based on its career prospects:

14. Students are more likely to choose media studies as a major to pursue in higher education based on the influence of the people around them:

Section D – **Management** (Indicate 1 – Strongly disagree, 2 – Disagree, 3 – Neither agree nor disagree, 4 – Agree, 5 – Strongly agree)

This section talks about management practices in higher education institutions.

15. It is the HEIs responsibility to provide a quality tertiary program for students:

16. Higher education institutions will be able to attract, retain and motivate educators if total quality management (TQM) is being practiced in their organisation:

17. Adopting total quality management (TQM) practices can improve HEIs' reputation and increase their enrolment:

18. Potential students are more likely to enrol at a higher education institute based on its stellar reputation:

Section E – **Social and economy** (Indicate 1 – Strongly disagree, 2 – Disagree, 3 – Neither agree nor disagree, 4 – Agree, 5 – Strongly agree)

This section talks about media studies' contribution to social and economic development.

19. Traditional media and new media are equally effective at influencing civic engagement within society:

20. People are more engaged and connected civically through the mass media:

21. The ability of HEIs to produce competent graduates will add value to the media industry:

22. As an individual who is interested in a career in the media industry, I would consider it if I knew that it was a stable industry that contributes to the economy:

Section F – **Marketing** (Indicate 1 – Strongly disagree, 2 – Disagree, 3 – Neither agree nor disagree, 4 – Agree, 5 – Strongly agree)

This section discusses the use of strategic marketing to promote media studies in higher education.

23. Social media is the most powerful tool in promoting a product to the young adolescents market:

24. Social media marketing is a highly effective platform for a business like higher education institutions to reach prospect students to enrol in media studies:

25. For any higher education institution in Singapore, adopting an appropriate marketing concept will be essential and strategic:

Appendix B

Figure 2. Semi-autonomous institutions diploma intake, enrolment, graduates

13.1 INTAKE, ENROLMENT AND GRADUATES OF LASALLE AND NAFA BY COURSE: DIPLOMA (FULL-TIME), 2020						
Courses	Intake		Enrolment		Graduates	
	Total	Female	Total	Female	Total	Female
Total	1,204	832	3,543	2,453	1,092	769
Business & Administration	60	49	200	156	72	52
Design & Applied Arts	675	467	2,034	1,456	596	466
Fine & Performing Arts	377	268	1,034	709	329	209
Media Production	92	48	275	132	95	42

Figure 3. Semi-autonomous institutions diploma bar chart

Figure 4. Government institutions diploma intake, enrolment, graduates

14 INTAKE, ENROLMENT AND GRADUATES OF POLYTECHNICS BY COURSE (FULL-TIME), 2020						
Courses	Intake		Enrolment		Graduates	
	Total	Female	Total	Female	Total	Female
Total	21,014	10,012	66,933	31,855	22,260	10,803
Applied Arts	1,711	1,049	5,312	3,199	1,729	1,059
Architecture, Building & Real Estate	624	329	1,892	988	633	350
Business & Administration	4,156	2,521	13,124	7,975	4,603	2,785
Education	713	663	2,164	2,001	713	661
Engineering Sciences	5,919	1,224	19,531	4,220	6,327	1,363
Health Sciences	2,516	1,842	7,919	5,888	2,375	1,789
Humanities & Social Sciences	298	228	909	698	348	259
Information Technology	2,520	637	7,997	2,173	2,610	802
Law	108	60	328	210	93	62
Mass Communication	549	415	1,792	1,334	620	461
Natural & Mathematical Sciences	1,109	669	3,037	1,947	1,201	730
Services	791	375	2,928	1,222	1,008	482

Figure 5. Government institutions diploma bar chart

Figure 6. Semi-autonomous institutions degree intake, enrolment, graduates

13.2 INTAKE, ENROLMENT AND GRADUATES OF LASALLE AND NAFA BY COURSE: DEGREE (FULL-TIME), 2020

Courses	Intake		Enrolment		Graduates	
	Total	Female	Total	Female	Total	Female
Total	452	334	1,214	897	478	342
Design & Applied Arts	277	230	746	594	264	202
Fine & Applied Arts	39	33	114	96	33	29
Fine & Performing Arts	104	56	273	167	130	84
Media Production	32	15	81	40	51	27

Figure 7. Semi-autonomous institutions degree bar chart

Figure 8. Government universities intake, enrolment, graduates

15 INTAKE, ENROLMENT AND GRADUATES OF UNIVERSITIES ¹ BY COURSE (FULL-TIME), 2020						
Courses	Intake		Enrolment		Graduates	
	Total	Female	Total	Female	Total	Female
Total	20,976	10,384	76,082	37,992	17,534	8,754
Accountancy	1,368	812	4,982	2,759	1,411	812
Architecture, Building & Real Estate	483	304	2,023	1,183	426	258
Business & Administration	3,378	2,039	11,275	6,684	2,105	1,209
Dentistry	72	59	253	165	51	35
Education	184	153	690	577	145	115
Engineering Sciences	5,225	1,503	18,050	5,149	4,621	1,246
Fine & Applied Arts	384	251	1,517	911	429	272
Health Sciences	1,018	761	3,347	2,455	724	522
Humanities & Social Sciences	2,930	2,001	12,892	8,783	3,147	2,125
Information Technology	2,863	846	8,811	2,797	1,367	397
Law	463	259	1,823	907	394	204
Mass Communication	170	142	714	566	181	142
Medicine	477	224	2,178	1,020	386	178
Natural & Mathematical Sciences	1,679	891	6,713	3,624	1,928	1,127
Services	282	139	814	412	219	112

Figure 9. Government universities degree bar chart

Appendix C

Project Timeline

Task Name	Days Took To Complete
Part 1	
Confirmation of Supervisor	21/10/22 - 1
Dissertation Briefing Workshop	26/10/22 - 1
Confirmation of Research Topic	27/10/22 - 1
Research Proposal Submission	31/10/22 – 03/11/22 - 4
Part 2	
Analysis of Literature Review	10/11/22 – 05/12/22 - 26
Research Methodology	08/12/22 – 12/12/22 - 5
Develop Questionnaire	07/12/22 - 1
Pilot testing of Questionnaire	13/12/22 - 1
Distribute Research Questionnaire	14/12/22 - 1
Received Complete Questionnaire	28/12/22 - 14
Part 3	
Evaluation of Data	29/12/22 – 08/01/23 - 11
Compose Findings	09/01/23 – 15/01/23 - 7
Conclusion	17/01/23 – 24/01/23 - 8
Final Review & Submission via Turnitin	25/01/23 – 31/01/23 - 7

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AGREED MEETING SCHEDULE

This form should be completed at the beginning of the supervisory process. Supervisor and the student should retain a copy.

Students are entitled to FOUR hours (normally) of face-to-face individual supervision supplemented by an appropriate amount of e-mail support.

Student's Name: Muhammad Taufik

Supervisor: Frankie Yee

Proposed Dates of Meeting and Research Progress Monitoring:

1st Meeting Date: <u>25 Oct 2022</u>	Estimated Duration : <u>1hr</u>
2nd Meeting Date : <u>10 Nov 2022</u>	Estimated Duration : <u>30 mins</u>
3rd Meeting Date : <u>30 Nov2022</u>	Estimated Duration : <u>45 mins</u>
4th Meeting Date : <u>18 Dec2022</u>	Estimated Duration : <u>45 mins</u>
5th Meeting date : <u>31 Jan 2023</u>	Estimated Duration : <u>1 hr</u>

Agreed submission date of final draft: 01 Feb 2023

Student's signature Date: 31 Jan 2023

Supervisor's signature: Date: 31 Jan 2023

Roehampton Business School

Supervision record

Student's name: Muhammad Taufik

Supervisor's name: Mr Frankie Yee

Date of meeting: 25 Oct 2022

Time: 1 hr

From 7pm **to** 8pm

Written work submitted or other purpose of meeting:

First meeting with the student. Discussion of what needs to be covered for the research work. To agree on the time line to complete the research work.

Main topics/issues discussed, and action points agreed:

The student's intended research topic was discussed. Provided advice to the student on the appropriateness of the research topic and identified any possible ethical concerns. Went through what need to be included in each chapter.

Time, date and location of next meeting:

10 Nov 2022, 4pm, Zoom

Actions and agenda topics for next meeting:

Complete the research proposal. Review Chapter 1

Student's signature

Date: 25 Oct 2022

Supervisor's signature:

Date: 25 Oct 2022

This form should be completed at each supervisory meeting. Supervisor and the student should retain a copy.

Roehampton Business School

Supervision record

Student's name: Muhammad Taufik

Supervisor's name: Mr Frankie Yee

Date of meeting: 10 Nov 2022

Time: 30 mins

From 5pm **to** 5.30pm

Written work submitted or other purpose of meeting:

Complete Chapter 1 and half of Chapter 2.

Main topics/issues discussed, and action points agreed:

Reviewed the student's proposal. No major issues found. The student will need to rewrite the research objectives to provide a clearer structure.

Time, date and location of next meeting:

30 Nov, 7pm, Zoom

Actions and agenda topics for next meeting:

Complete Chapter 2 and questionnaire

Student's signature

Date: 10 Nov 2022

Supervisor's signature:

Date: 10 Nov 2022

*This form should be completed at **each** supervisory meeting. Supervisor and the student should retain a copy.*

Roehampton Business School

Supervision record

Student's name: Muhammad Taufik

Supervisor's name: Mr Frankie Yee

Date of meeting: 30 Nov 2022

Time: 45 mins

From 5pm **to** 5.45pm

Written work submitted or other purpose of meeting:

The student completed Chapters 1 and 2.

Main topics/issues discussed, and action points agreed:

Chapter 2 was very well presented. The literature review was good and a critical approach was adopted. We discussed the hypotheses and the research framework. A questionnaire was presented. A brief discussion on the data collection process.

Time, date and location of next meeting:

18 Dec 2022, 6pm, Zoom

Actions and agenda topics for next meeting:

Complete Chapter 3 and present the surveys conducted.

Student's signature

Date: 30 Nov 2022

Supervisor's signature:

Date: 30 Nov 2022

This form should be completed at each supervisory meeting. Supervisor and the student should retain a copy.

Roehampton Business School

Supervision record

Student's name: Muhammad Taufik

Supervisor's name: Mr Frankie Yee

Date of meeting: 18 Dec 2022

Time: 45 mins

From 4pm **to** 4.45pm

Written work submitted or other purpose of meeting:

Student completed Chapter 3 and started collecting data.

Main topics/issues discussed, and action points agreed:

The research method was justified. The questions asked were linked to the ROs. No major problems identified. Discussed the statistical tools needed for the research.

Time, date and location of next meeting:

10 Jan 2023, 4pm, Zoom

Actions and agenda topics for next meeting:

To complete Chapters 4 and 5. Prepare for final review

Student's signature

Date: 18 Dec 2022

Supervisor's signature:

Date: 18 Dec 2022

This form should be completed at each supervisory meeting. Supervisor and the student should retain a copy.

Roehampton Business School

Supervision record

Student's name: Muhammad Taufik

Supervisor's name: Mr Frankie Yee

Date of meeting: 31 Jan 2023

Time: 1 hr

From 4pm **to** 5pm

Written work submitted or other purpose of meeting:

Final meeting with student for review

Main topics/issues discussed, and action points agreed:

The student has completed the research and is ready to submit. No major issues found and the student was briefed on the documents that need to be submitted.

Student's signature

Date: 10 Jan 2023

Supervisor's signature:

Date: 10 Jan 2023

This form should be completed at each supervisory meeting. Supervisor and the student should retain a copy.

Ethics discussion and agreement

I have discussed the ethical considerations associated with my proposed research with my supervisor. The following points were covered:

1. Rights of participants: what participation involves, right to withdraw
2. Confidentiality of findings: who has access to the findings, anonymity of participants/organisation.
3. Data protection: making it clear how the data will be gathered, stored and destroyed.
4. Institutional reputation: ensuring that the research is conducted in a professional manner, including all written communication.

If my research methods change in any way, I will re-discuss any ethical issues with my supervisor.

Name of student : Muhammad Taufik

Name of supervisor : Yee Kok Wah Frankie

Signed (student) _____

Date : 10 Nov 2022

Signed (supervisor) _____

Date : 10 Nov 2022